

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B172
Date: 13 Feb 2006
Take Off: 15:25:03
Landing: 17:04:52
Flight Time: 1h39m49s

Campaign: DODO
Trials Instructions: Biomass / Aerosol Sampling
Operating Area: North of Dakar, over ocean

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	VACC/PAN/WAS	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds
7	AVAPS	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Alison Perry	FAAM
10	AMS 2	Gerard Capes	University of Manchester
11	Wet Neph	James Bowles	Met Office
12	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
13	SWS/SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
14	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
16	Engineer	John Kitchen	Avalon Aero
17	CVI/CCN/CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
18			

Flight Track:

B172 Track 13-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b172
 Date: 13 Feb 2006
 Project: DODO
 Location: North of Dakar, over ocean

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
152155		taxy	-.07 kft	359	
152503		T/O	-.09 kft	359	from Nouadhibou
153849	154959	Profile 1	4.9 - 0.05 kft	359	500 ft/min
154959	155504	Run 1	0.05 kft	359	500 ft/min
155504	155834	Profile 2	0.05 - 1.9 kft	359	
155834	161452	Run 2	1.9 kft	359	
161452	162027	Profile 3	1.9 - 5.0 kft	359	
162027	165703	Run 3	5.0 - 4.9 kft	359	
170452		Land	0.10 kft	359	
170950		standstill	0.10 kft	359	14'44.56N, 17'28.30W

B172 Track 13-FEB-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DODO: dust in-situ sampling and radiation studies

Flight No: B171

Date: 13th February 2006

Trial objectives:

To perform in-situ microphysical and chemical measurements of Saharan dust aerosol over the ocean.

Location:

Over sea areas between point A (22°00'N, 20°00'W) and point B (24°00'N, 20°00'W)

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric dust. Cloudless skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Re-fuel at Nouadhibou.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar.
2. Profile to FL240 at 1000ft/min heading north [25mins, T=25mins]
3. Transit at range speed towards point A via GUNET [45mins, T=70mins]
4. Profile descent at science speed from FL240 to FL050 at 1000ft/min to reach point A [20mins, T=90mins]
5. SLR at FL050 heading north [20mins, T=110mins]
6. Profile descent from FL050 to 50ft towards point B at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and at 500ft/min below 3000ft [10mins, T=120mins]
7. Carry two 10min SLRs at 100ft on reciprocal headings orientated north-south [25mins, T=145mins]
8. Carry out a 15min SLR at two different levels within the dust plume orientated north-south (suggest 2000ft and FL050) with profile climbs between the levels [40mins, T=185mins]
9. Carry out a 15min SLR at two different levels within the dust plume orientated east-west (suggest 2000ft and FL050) with profile climbs between the levels [40mins, T=225mins]
10. Profile descent to 600ft [10mins, T=235mins]
11. Perform four orbits at maximum angle of bank at 600ft altitude [10mins, T=245mins]
12. Profile to FL150 at 1000ft/min towards Nouadhibou [10mins, T=255mins]
13. SLR at FL150 to Nouadhibou [45mins, T=300mins]
14. Land Nouadhibou.

Re-fuel

15. Take off from Nouadhibou.

If further science required:

16. Profile to FL150 at 1000ft/min towards point B [15mins, T=15mins]
17. SLR at FL150 [20mins, T=35mins]
18. Profile descent from FL150 to reach point B at 50ft at 1000ft/min above 3000ft and at 500ft/min below 3000ft [20mins, T=55mins]
19. Carry out SLRs within the dust plume [35mins, T=90mins]
20. Profile ascent to FL240 at 1000ft/min heading south [20mins, T=110mins]
21. Transit at high speed to Dakar [70mins, T=180mins]
22. Land Dakar.

Else:

Transit direct to Dakar.

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet

Flight B172

13th February 2006

Summary of the weather conditions:

Local dust present in the area of Nouadibou but clear, cloudless skies to the south en route to Dakar.

Scientific Aims;

The flight aimed to locate and sample a dust storm, which was predicted by the CAM and NAME models to be advecting dust from northern Mauritania and Western Sahara westwards over the eastern Atlantic in the operating region to the north of Dakar en return route from Nouadibou to Dakar.

Points defined:

Dakar airfield (13°29'N, 2°10'E), Nouadibou (20° 55' 59N 17° 1' 48W)

Summary of the flight:

Due to the absence of a ground power unit at Nouadibou science power was lost and only a skeleton instrument fit was enabled for the short transit from Nouadibou to Dakar. Local dust increased significantly during the refuel ($>250 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$) but after profiling out of the airfield southward this had not advected away to the south of the region. Visibility was greater than 50 nautical miles for the transit with no evidence of transported dust. There were some signs of an elevated biomass layer at around 6000' over land to the east but no evidence of a perturbed oceanic background. The biomass layer extended as far south as Dakar.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B. 171B**
 FAAM © 2004

 Date 13/2/06

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:25:03	T/O				20C 20kts.
15:42	RUN				
15:38:49	PROFILE 1 DESCENT	5000' 100'	S		Heading South towards Dakar 30nm offshore up to 250 mm ⁻¹ at surface and a separate layer at 2000 ft at 150 mm ⁻¹ . However this was local production and little dust if any in profile down.
15:49:59	RUN 1	100'			
15:55:04	RUN 1 END	100'			
15:55:04	PROFILE 2 START	100' → 2000'	S		
15:58:34	PROFILE 2 END	2000'	S		
15:58:34	RUN 2 START	2000'			Now 70nmiles off coast and coastline vis at 2000'
16:14:52	RUN 2 END	2000'			
16:14:52	PROFILE 3 ASCENT	2000 → 5000'			
16:20:27	PROFILE 3 END	5000'			
16:20:27	RUN 3 START	5000'			
16:30					negl scatt ⇒ 20 & 50 mm ⁻¹ later below 2000' and < 10 mm ⁻¹ at 5000'
16:33					50nmiles to coast and visible.
16:45					Some signs of elevated layer at around 5000' over land to East but no sign over Ocean.

layer extends over Dakar area.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B171

Date: 13/02/06 **Operator:** MAP **DRS Time:** 06:45:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 3 of 4**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:52:00	100	0.10	Off	10	10												
11:54:00	140	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
11:56:00	80	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
11:58:00	90	0.09	Off	10	10												
12:00:00	70	0.09	Off	10	Noise												
12:02:00	100	0.10	Off	10	8												
12:04:00	100	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
12:06:00	90	0.10	Off	10	Noise												
12:08:00	90	0.10	Off	10	2												
12:10:00	80	0.10	Off	10	2												
12:12:00	85	0.10	Off	10	2												
12:15:00																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 8 from FL045	
12:15:45	80	0.09	4	10	2											FL040	
12:17:07	380	0.10		50	8											FL030	
12:18:50	450	0.10		50	8											FL020	
12:20:36																End of Profile 8 & Start Run 7 @ 1000'	
12:21:00	690	0.10		40	8												
12:23:00	700	0.09		40	10												
12:25:00	730	0.09		50	10												
12:27:00	730	0.09	Off	40	9												
12:29:00	680	0.09	Off	50	9												
12:31:00	750	0.09	Off	50	9												
12:33:00	770	0.09	Off	50	3												
12:35:00	740	0.09	Off	50	10												
12:37:00	770	0.09	Off	80	8												
12:39:00	750	0.09	Off	80	10												
12:41:00	735	0.09	Off	80	9												
12:43:00	700	0.09	Off	80	10												
12:45:00	675	0.09	Off	80	8												
12:47:00	700	0.09	Off	90	10												
12:49:00	700	0.09	Off	100	10												
12:51:00	620	0.09	Off	50	3												
12:52:25																End of Run 7	
12:52:34																Start Profile 9 from 1000'	
12:53:31	100	0.09	Off	10	1											FL020	
12:54:17	65	0.09	Off	5	1											FL030	
12:54:57	60	0.09	Off	5	1											FL040	
12:55:45	50	0.09	Off	5												End of Profile 9 @ FL050	
15:38:18	90	0.09	Off	5												Start Profile 10 from FL050	
15:40:58	100	0.10	Off	5												FL040	
15:42:55	100	0.10	Off	10	Noise											FL030	
15:45:10	100	0.09	Off	10	Noise											FL020	
15:49:58																End of Profile 10 & Start Run 8 @ 100'	
15:50:00	130	0.09	Off	20	Noise												
15:52:00	310	0.08	Off	20	Noise												
15:54:00	145	0.09	Off	20	Noise												

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B172 (called B171A in the cloud physics logs)

Date:

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC	X	
Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data	X	
Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	X	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory	X	
PMSDATA: on FLOODS	X	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS	X	
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	X	
c) Output directory: PMSDATA:	X	
d) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
e) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT	X	Note the calibration file used
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	X	
c) TAS in processing: Y	X	
d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0	X	
e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file.	X	
Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt	X	CAL27022006.TXT
Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]	X	Zero glitches
f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N	N	Yes only if gross errors occur
g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	-	in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE		
a) enter:		
!path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]'		
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!		
b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat',	X	
'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto	X	
1st argument is output file from 5)	X	
2nd argument is the MFD	X	
3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format	X	
c) exit	X	
6) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp	X	
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name	X	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	
7) CHECKS:	n/a	
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?	No cloud	
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B172 (B171B in cloud physics logs)

Date:

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	X	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	X	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	X X	
4) Log on to FLOODS	X	Condor
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	X	B171A+B171B in zip file (use B171B only here)
6) In PVWAVE	X	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	No bad blocks
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	X	
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	X	B171B.DAT
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat		
iii) exit	X	<i>B172_SEADAS.DAT</i>
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	X	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	X	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
d) Comment string:	X	
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
g) Read 2DC: Y	X	
h) Read 2DP: Y	X	
i) Secondary data Y	X	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	X	
k) cmd.str: Y	X	
l) Auto time correction: N	X	
m) Full length secondary: N	X	
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10		
iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	X	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end.
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	X	
c) File generation: Hit enter	X	
d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data	x	0
e) TAS: Y	X	
f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	X	
g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty	X	
h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	0	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	240000	
j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5	0.2	
k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown	8	Note the particle type
l) Coefficient choice: 2	2	
m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	X	NO 2D DATA DURING B172
10) In PVWAVE		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!		
ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'		
iii) exit		
11) MODIFY	n/a	NO 2D DATA DURING B172
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D		
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX		
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name		
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?	n/a	NO 2D DATA DURING B172

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B172****Date:**

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	X	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	X X	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	X	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	X	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	X	
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here	X	Channel 1
e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec	X	1.6 ml/sec
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	X	0
g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
3) In PVWAVE		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!		
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	X	
iii) exit	X	
4) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	MFDC
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: Bnnn

Date: DD/MM/YY

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC				
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments		
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC				
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults				
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc]		Defaults in [square brackets] As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated		
2) Ftp transfer to BADC				
- stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary				

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:Bnnn*. * outdir:Bnnn_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** Bnnn**Date:** DD/MM/YY

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt Bnnn_FFSSP.raw Bnnn_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
- rename Bnnn.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B171 a*

Location: *N Mainlandia*

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Date: *13-2-6*

Operator(s): *VANCE*

Resolution: *1*

Gain A: *2* B: *2*

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
<i>0630</i>	<i>Startup</i>	<i>B171</i>								<i>OK</i>
<i>063222</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>B171a</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>23N</i>	<i>N19</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>-187</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>CH1x1 (checking)</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>063626</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>B171b</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>30.8</i>	<i>21N</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>-189.9</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>CH2x1 (")</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>063851</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>B171c</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>30.6</i>	<i>N22</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>1Rx1 (")</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>064114</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>B171d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>N22</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>Z1x1 (")</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>064308</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>B171e</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>N23</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>N1x1 (")</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>06</i>		<i>B171f</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>N24</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>N1x5 (")</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>[Shut down for copying/backing-up of files etc. — restart. OK]</i>										
<i>084911</i>	<i>T/O (PI)</i>								<i>(~ 5.6/8 alt cut)</i>	<i>B det gain 4 looks good on Z</i>
<i>091011</i>		<i>B171 G</i>							<i>(Playing w' shutter - looks like HBB sh. recovers in < 30 sec)</i>	<i>TAT 250K</i>
<i>0920</i>	<i>Transit</i>									
<i>092322</i>	<i>" FL240?</i>	<i>B171 H</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>1.5</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>CH1x2</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>092647</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>B171 I</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>1.5</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>CH1x1</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>092852</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>B171 J</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>0.2</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>Z1x4 (OK)</i>	<i>Clear above. Scattered (1/2) Cuv</i>
<i>093142</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>B171 K</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>-2.1</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>21.7</i>	<i>CH1x1</i>	
<i>093316</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>B171 L</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>-1.7</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>22</i>	<i>Z1x4 gain B:4</i>	<i>(TAT Tol -24, -39) OK</i>
<i>093717</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>B171 M</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>-3.2</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>CH1x1</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>093844</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>B171 N</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>-3</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>Z1x4 G(2,4)</i>	<i>OK</i>
<i>094214</i>		<i>B171 P</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>71</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>-3.7</i>	<i>-190</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>CH1x1 G(2,2)</i>	<i>OK</i>

ARIES flight log

Flight: B171 a

Location: Mauritania

page 2 of 6

Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	A GAIN B	Comments
094449	"	B171 Q	c/o	70	30	-4	-190	18	Z1x2	G(2,2)	OK
094725	"	B171 S	0	70	31	-5	-190	15	Z1x1	G(2,2)	OK
094847	"	B171 T	C	71	31	-5	-190	16	CH1x1	G(2,2)	OK
095040?	"	B171 U	C	71	31	-4			N1 x1	2+ 2	OK
095125	"	B171 *V	C	71	31	-4	-190	18	N1 x1	2- 2	OK
095227	"	B171 W	C	71	31	-5	-190	18	CH1x1	2 2	OK
095427	"	B171 X	C	71	31	-4	-190	19	CH1x1	2 2	OK
095538	"	B171 Y	c/o	71	31	-4	-190	19	Z1x2	2 4	OK
095738	"	B171 Z	0	71	31	-6	-190	15	Z1x1	2 4	OK
095853	"	B171 ϕ	C	71	31	-6	-190	15	CH1x2	2 2	OK
100112	"	B171 1	0	70	31	-6	-190	17	Z1x3	2 4	OK
100403	"	B171 2	C	71	31	-7	-190	15	CH1x1	2 2	OK
100517	"	B171 3	0	70	30	-7	-190	15	Z1x3	2 4	SP2, 100547 OK
102147	R1 Flow50	B171 4	C	71	30	2.5	-190	22	CH1x1	2 2	OK
102303	"	B171 5	0	71	30	6.3	-190	21	Z1x4	2 4	OK
102649	"	B171 6	C	71	31	10.9	-190	19.9	CH1x1	2 2	OK 1028 EoR
102803	" / p/R Flow40	B171 7	0	70	30	11	-190	20	Z1x4	2 4	running on. SR 2:1?
103216	R 2.1	B171 8	C	71	30	13	-190	20	CH1x1	2 2	OK
103333	"	B171 9	0	70	31	14	-190	21	Z1x4	2 4	(between A & B on chart)

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B171a*

Location: *Mauritania*

page 3 of 6

Date: *13-2-6*

Operator(s): *VANCE*

Resolution: *1*

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	GAIN A/B	Comments
103720	R2-1	^C C 171a	C	71	31	15	-190	20	CH1x1	2 2	OK
103908	"	C171b	O	71	31	15	-190	21	Z1x1	2 4	(104040, EOR) OK
104021	ER	C171c	C	70	31	15	-190	21	CH1x1	2 2	OK
104836	R3-1, 100'	C171D	C	71	31	17	-190	23	CH1x1	2 2	OK
104950	R3-1	C171E	O	70	30	19	-190	23	Z1x3	2 4	EOR 105205 OK
105540	R4-1	C171F	O/C	70					CH1x1	2 2	OK
105707	R4-1	C171G	O	71	32	21	-190	24	Z1x4	2 4	OK
110101	R4-1	C171H	C	71	32	21	-190	23	CH1x1		OK
110300		ARIES I							Software restarted to close files		
110327	R4-1	C171J	C	71	31	21	-190	24	CH1x1	2 2	OK
110445	"	C171K	O	70	31	21	-190	24	Z1x3	2 4	OK
110744	"	C171L	C	71	32	21	-190	24	CH1x1	2 2	OK
110910	"	C171M	O	71	32	21	-190	24	Z1x3	2 4	OK
111207	"	C171N	C	71	32	21	-190	24	CH1x1	2 2	OK
111315	"	C171O	O	70	32	22	-190	25	Z1x3	2 4	OK
111623	"	C171P	C	71	32	22	-190	25	CH1x1	2 2	OK
111752	"	C171Q	O	71	32	21	-190	25	Z1x1	2 4	OK
111858	"	C171R	O	71	32	22	-190	25	Z1x1	2 4	OK
111958	"	C171S	O	71	32	22	-190	25	Z1x1	2 4	OK

14 min

ARIES flight log

Flight: B171a

Location: *Mannitonia*

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Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	GAIN A B	Comments
112111	R4.1	C171T	C	71	32	22	-190	25	CH1x1	2 2	OK
112228	R4.1	C171U	O	71	33	22	-190	25	Z1x3	2 4	(EOR 102323) Running on - OK
112545	R5.1	C171V	C	71	32	22	-190	25	CH1x1	2 2	OK
112705	"	C171W	O	71	32	22	-190	25	Z1x3	2 4	TAT 15° Td 14° OK
113014	"	C171X	C	71	33	22	-190	26	CH1x1	2 2	OK
113132	"	C171Y	O	70	33	22	-190	26	Z1x3	2 4	OK
113432	"	C171Z	C	71	33	22	-190	26	CH1x1	2 2	OK
113554	"	C171φ	O	71	32	22	-190	26	Z1x3	2 4	OK
113902	"	C1711	C	71	33	22	-190	26	CH1x1	2 2	OK
114015	"	C1712	O	70	33	23	-190	26	Z1x3	2 4	OK
114327	"	C1713	C	71	33	23	-190	26	CH1x1	2 2	OK
115605	R / 5000'	C1714	C	71	31	21	-190	28	CH1x1	2 2	OK
115728	"	C1715	O	71	32	20	-190	27	Z1x3	2 4	OK
120037	"	C1716	C	71	31	18	-190	26	CH1x1	2 2	Noisy 1GM p start / OK
120147	"	C1717	C	71	31	18	-190	26	CH1x1	2 2	" / OK
120303 [?]	"	C1718	O	70	32	17	-190	25	Z1x3	2 4	OK
120621	"	C1719	C	71	31	17	-190	25	CH1x1	2 2	OK
120736	"	D171a	O	70	31	17	-190	25	Z1x3	2 4	OK
121033	"	D171b	C	71	31	16	-190	24	CH1x1	2 2	OK

ARIES flight log

Flight: B171a

Location: Mauritania

page 5 of 6

Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): WAJCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	GAIN		Comments
										A	B	
121205	R 5000'	D171C	0	71	32	11	-191	25	Z1x3	2	4	OK CoR 121450
121520		D171D	g/c	71	31	16.3	-191	24	CH1x1	2	2	OK
122046	R7.1/1000'	D171E	C	70	31	17	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK
122207	"	D171F	0	71	30	18	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
122509	"	D171G	C	71	31	20	-190	25	CH1x1	2	2	OK
122635	"	D171H	0	71	31	20	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
122941	"	D171I	C	71	31	20	-190	25	CH1x1	2	2	OK
123055?	"	D171J	0	71	31	21	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	OK
123415	"	D171K	C	71	31	21	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK
123603	"	D171L	0	71	32	21	-190	26	CH1x1 Z1x3	2	4	OK
123907	"	D171M	C	71	31	21	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	OK BORED...
124036	"	D171N	0	70	32	21	-190	26	Z1x3	2	4	
124327	"	D171O	C	71	32				fell over			file handles.
124629	"	D171P?	C	71	31	26	-190	27	CH1x1	2	2	OK
124750	"	D171R	0	70	31	21	-190	26.4	Z1x1	2	4	OK
125050	"	D171S	C	71	31	21	-190	26	CH1x1	2	2	} some V-mousey cold IGMs but ran OK
125210?	"	D171T	C	71	31	21	-190	27	CH1x1	2	2	
1300	- shut down for refuelling.											
1521	Restart.											

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13171 b

Location: Mauritania

page 6 of 6

Date: 13-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: B:

Notes:

B171
↑
B172
↓

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	GAIN		Comments
										A	B	
153243	Rtn transit	D171V	c	71	31	24	-190	29	CH1X1	2	2	OK
		D172W	c									OK
1545:43	"	D172X	c	71	32	20.7	-190	25	CH1X1	1	8	oops!
1547:09	"	D172Y	o	70	32	22	-190	26	CH1X1			OK
1549:51	" R1	D172Z	c	71	33	23.6	-160	27	CH1X1	2	2	OK
1551:28	" 100'	D172φ	o	70	33	24	-189.9	27	Z1X3	2	8	OK
1554:11	"	D1721	c	72	33	24	-190	27	CH1X1	2	2	OK
1558:46	R2, 2000'	D1722	c	71	32	24	-190	28	CH1X1	2	2	OK
1600:43	"	D1723	φ	71	32	24	-191	28	Z1X5	2	8	Shutter opened ~160150/OK
1605:22	"	D1724	c	71	33	24	-191	28	CH1X1	2	2	OK
1608:03	"	D1725	o	70	34	24	-190	28	CH1X1	2	2	OK TAT 18 Tol 7.5
1609:20	"	D1726	φ	70.7	33	24	-191	28.3	Z1X5	2	8	OK
		Pointing bits off to cool CBB										
1624		end to rad. science										

Flight leader nextgen
 then as B172 as warning
 because with limited parameters
 have set ARIES to B172 but
 can't turn it off with file allow
 because B171 kept off.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 172

Date: 13th February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	N	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	N	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	N		
TWC	N		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	N	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	N	ADA	N
CO	N	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	Y	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	Y	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B172

Date: 13 February 2006

Instruments

1. Upper and Lower Pyrometers – signal noisy
2. JW not operated
3. Limited instrumentation run as pre-flight curtailed out of Nouadhibou.
- 4.
- 5.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

B172 was a continuation post refuel of B171. Some instrument logs were continued on the B171 sheets. If the information you seek is not contained in this pdf file please check the most recent B171 file.

The following log sheets are not available for flight B172:

Log	Reason
SWS / SHIMS	See B171 for log.
Wet Nephelometer	No log as instrument not operated on this return transit of B171.
Filters	Any B172 information is NOT part of B171 log. No B172 log sheet is available so probably no data was recorded.
WAS	No WAS on B172 (Jim McQuaid 21 Apr 2006)
Tubes & Air Sample Bags	Any B172 information is NOT part of B171 log.
PSAP	No log taken/available?
AVAPS	No log taken/available?
CCN	Any B172 information is NOT part of B171 log. No B172 log sheet, so probably no data recorded. First half of flight included in B171 flight Folder pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
Core Chemistry	
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
VACC	No log is taken/provided for VACC
PAN	No log is taken/provided for PAN

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Included on B171 tapes.

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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